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RESEARCH-ARTICLE

An Evaluation of Open Source Data Anonymisation Tools for Medical Data

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An Evaluation of Open Source Data Anonymisation Tools for Medical Data

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Abstract

Medical data is inherently multimedia in nature. A single patient record typically contains diverse data types, including multimodal medical images, sensor signals, and Electronic Health Records (EHRs).

Given the recent revolution in Artificial Intelligence (AI), these medical datasets are crucial for a wide range of AI-based clinical applications. However, sharing this data presents several significant challenges e.g. data privacy. Data privacy tools enable data sharing and utility while ensuring the confidentiality of such sensitive information. Data anonymisation allows sharing an anonymised version of the dataset, which may protect the privacy of the individuals and organisations involved.

This study provides a comprehensive evaluation of popular open-source anonymisation tools by assessing their practical performance and compliance when applied to sensitive medical datasets that must adhere to legal frameworks. It compares these tools across 12 key dimensions on 3 different datasets of different size.

Our findings show a trade-off: feature-rich tools such as ARX and sdcMicro require a significant learning curve and specialist technical knowledge. Conversely, other tools, such as GreenMask, Neosync, and ClustEm4Ano, offer greater user-friendliness but are lacking in important capabilities. The study highlights key gaps across the multimedia, especially in the medical domains e.g., the weak support for healthcare ontologies and the absence of standardised evaluation benchmarks.

CCS Concepts

• **Computing methodologies** → **Artificial intelligence**; • **Security and privacy**;

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1 Introduction

The advancement of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in clinical applications requires access to large-scale medical datasets. These datasets are multimedia in nature, integrating diverse data types such as multimodal medical images, sensor signals, and Electronic Health Records (EHRs) [25].

However, sharing such data is impeded by many challenges. One major challenge is the data privacy [26]. A number of studies have shown that even seemingly de-identified health datasets are vulnerable to re-identification attacks [7, 21]. Anonymisation tools help to increase data utility while ensuring the confidentiality of sensitive information by sharing a modified version of the dataset to protect the privacy of the individuals and organisations involved. Good privacy tools should meet legal regulations such as the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) [1] and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [28].

Data privacy tools often leverage established anonymisation algorithms like k -anonymity [27], l -diversity [14], and t -closeness [12] to protect sensitive information, with open-source anonymisation tools having gained widespread adoption. More recently, a newer generation of developer-focused tools has emerged, which prioritise modern data needs. Table 1 shows the selected open-source anonymisation tools.

Several studies on data anonymisation tools have provided valuable frameworks and taxonomies [22, 29], yet they suffer from some limitations. Mainly, most evaluations focused either on theoretical privacy methods such as k -anonymity and l -diversity or on a narrow subset of tabular datasets, overlooking the growing relevance of multimedia-rich healthcare environments. Moreover, there is a lack of standardised evaluation frameworks focused on practical.

This study addresses a gap in the literature by providing an up-to-date, empirical evaluation of popular data anonymisation tools. It utilises a standardised system that incorporates industry-specific factors and general software quality criteria. By offering this organised and practical comparison, this study provides valuable insights for the digital, multimedia, and healthcare communities. It supports the safer and more efficient reuse of health data, which is crucial for clinical innovation, scientific research, and public health initiatives.

2 Methodology

This section explains our methodology to evaluate the open source data anonymisation tools for healthcare data. Our test framework builds on principles such as performance and usability metrics, which have been used in the literature [6, 11]. We used an evaluation

Table 1: List of Selected Open-Source Anonymisation Tools

Tool	Organisation	Date	GitHub
ARX	Technical University of Munich, Germany	2012	https://github.com/arx-deidentifier/arx
sdcmicro	Vienna University of Technology, Austria	2017	https://github.com/sdcTools/sdcMicro
Amnesia	Athena Research Center, Greece	2023	https://github.com/dTsitsigkos/Amnesia
Neosync	Neon, Community/Inactive	2023	https://github.com/nucleuscloud/neosync
GreenMask	GreenmaskIO, Community	2023	https://github.com/GreenmaskIO/greenmask
SynDiffix	Max Planck Institute, Germany	2024	https://github.com/diffix/syndiffix
ClustEm4Ano	EAsyAnon Project, Germany	2024	https://github.com/EAsyAnon/ClustEm4Ano
μ -ANT	Universitat Rovira i Virgili, Spain	2019	https://github.com/CrisesUrv/microaggregation-based_anonymization_tool

methodology that involves empirical testing in order to perform a practical assessment.

Tools Selection

This study focuses on open-source anonymisation tools to allow research and result reproducibility. Commercial tools are excluded from this study because they impose financial, licensing, or access restrictions, which make them unsuitable for academic benchmarking and research.

A number of open source data anonymisation tools were selected from several public sources i.e., a public portal maintained by the German NFDI4Health cooperation [19], GitHub¹ repositories, and literature. Each selected tool in this study was chosen based on specific criteria, in particular: accessibility as an open-source project, availability of documentation, and support for structured and healthcare data. These selected tools are listed in Table 1. The table includes information about the origin and the date of the tools in addition to their GitHub links.

Evaluation Framework

We use a standardised evaluation approach that incorporates general software quality criteria and healthcare-specific anonymisation needs to guarantee uniform evaluation across all the tools. This is informed by ISO/IEC 25010 [16, 20], OpenBRR [15], and prior empirical studies [18, 29], consisting of both software engineering quality and domain-specific criteria. Additionally, we include compatibility with common medical data protocols, visual feedback mechanisms, data utility and information loss metrics, support for attacker models, and multilingual support.

The ISO/IEC 25010 software quality standards and earlier evaluation models, including the one put forward by Razi [22], serve as the basis for our proposed framework. The comparison criteria/dimensions include:

- (1) Anonymisation algorithm: The number, type, and date of implemented anonymisation algorithms.
- (2) Usability: The tools should have simple installation procedure, workflows, a friendly Graphical User Interface (GUI), simple Command Line Interface (CLI). Usability remains a known barrier for adoption in healthcare settings [6, 13]. The design choice reflects a broader trend where modern privacy

tools may prioritise operational ease over documentation or validation, as seen in recent studies [5].

- (3) Risk Assessment: The assessment of the likelihood that an individual could be re-identified after the anonymisation process.
- (4) Software Quality: The quality of the software is based on different characteristics like reliability, functional suitability, and maintainability. In some relevant studies, e.g., [16], the tools are also evaluated based on software quality.
- (5) Medical Data: The suitability of the tool to be used in the medical data context. The healthcare data consist of quasi-identifiers frequently found in EHRs and ICD-10² codes and need to be aligned with requirements emphasized in [8, 30].
- (6) Legal Compliance: The tool should comply with legal frameworks such as GDPR and HIPAA. There has been recent work calling for improved support for compliance documentation in tool chains for health data governance [4].
- (7) Interoperability: Evaluating how easily each tool can be integrated, automated, or extended within other software systems or workflows. The tools should support Application Programming Interfaces (APIs)³ and CI/CD⁴ pipelines.
- (8) Format Compatibility: How well the tool handles different types of datasets. The tools should support EHRs and HL7⁵/FHIR⁶ protocols.
- (9) Data Utility: Usefulness of the anonymised output data compared to the original data.
- (10) Visualisation: The support for visualisation of the anonymised data [29].
- (11) Attack Simulation: The ability of the tool to model and measure privacy risk by simulating different re-identification attacks [2].
- (12) Multilingual Support: The ability of the tool to accommodate international users. Measured on the basis of how many languages or regional settings it supports.

Each criterion was rated on a 0 to 2 ordinal scale, where 0 indicates no support, 1 indicates limited or partial support, and 2 indicates strong or full support. This approach has been used in

¹<https://github.com>

²<https://icd.who.int/browse10/2019>

³<https://github.com/resources/articles/software-development/what-is-an-api>

⁴<https://about.gitlab.com/topics/ci-cd/>

⁵<https://www.hl7.org>

⁶<https://fhir.org>

previous studies [6, 16, 18, 29, 30]. To guarantee platform consistency, all tools were installed and tested on a macOS Sequoia 15.6.1 system and Ubuntu 24.04 on MacBook Pro A2141 2019 device.

Datasets

We utilised three healthcare datasets representing a range of data complexities and sizes. The three datasets simulate electronic health record (EHR) structures, incorporating quasi-identifiers, sensitive clinical attributes, and tabular relational formats.

- Patient Treatment Classification dataset [24]: A small-sized realistic dataset with 3,300 records and 11 attributes.
- Asthma Synthetic Medical dataset [17]: A medium-sized synthetic dataset with 10,000 records and 17 attributes.
- Multilingual Synthetic EHR Dataset Bundle dataset [23]: a large-scale synthetic dataset with 200,000 records and 24 attributes.

Longitudinal nested data structures were not utilised as they can be reshaped into a tabular format, allowing for the consistent application of our established evaluation methodology.

3 Results

To ensure reproducible evaluation, we executed a standardised anonymisation across all selected tools. For each tool, the process involved importing datasets of varying complexities, configuring and executing anonymisation algorithms, and exporting the results. Usability evaluations were conducted by performing typical user workflows, such as dataset upload, configuration, and anonymisation execution, assessing both GUI-based interactions and command-line integrations.

The summary of the tools comparison is given in Table 2. Figure 1 visualises the support level of each tested tool for some metrics due to space constraints, the detailed results are discussed below:

- (1) Anonymisation algorithm: ARX supports many algorithms and offers configurable implementations. sdcMicro supports k-anonymity and l-diversity, though its setup is more manual. μ -ANT concentrates on micro-aggregation-based anonymisation, limiting support for some many anonymisation algorithms. Amnesia's support is limited to k-anonymity. Recent tools like Neosync and GreenMask primarily use value masking and pseudonymization, thus lacking the support of many anonymisation algorithms. SynDiffix employs synthetic data creation combined with noise mechanisms for query-based anonymisation, diverging from typical anonymisation algorithms. ClustEm4Ano uniquely presents a generalization hierarchy based on clustering and embeddings.
- (2) Usability: Amnesia, GreenMask, and Neosync ranked high due to their simple workflows, simple GUI, and low installation complexity. GreenMask and Neosync concentrated on a developer-centric CI/CD pipeline integration with documentation, whereas Amnesia provides a web-based GUI and CLI interface. Similarly, ARX offers both GUI and CLI, though it can be complex for users unfamiliar with anonymisation algorithms due to many configuration options. For non-technical users, μ -ANT and ClustEm4Ano are less usable due to their reliance on CLI with a few number of instructions.

- (3) Risk Assessment: ARX provided configurable risk analysis modules, including record-level re-identification risk and attacker models. sdcMicro supports disclosure risk metrics through R scripts. Though SynDiffix lacks a record-level risk analysis, it incorporates privacy-preserving query behaviour aligned with differential privacy principles. Tools like Amnesia, μ -ANT, GreenMask, Neosync, and ClustEm4Ano currently lack risk assessment functionality.
- (4) Software Quality: GreenMask and Neosync have developer-friendly design, comprehensive documentation, and easy integration. Also, due to the simple web interface, Amnesia also performed well. In contrast, ClustEm4Ano and μ -ANT lacked thorough documentation and offered poor usability. Despite robust functionality, ARX was challenging for users new to anonymisation algorithms to install and configure. sdcMicro also needs technical expertise in statistical disclosure control.
- (5) Medical Data: ARX and sdcMicro support processing quasi-identifiers found in EHRs and ICD-10 codes while also supporting structured data anonymisation. ClustEm4Ano supports nominal categorical data, valuable for clinical text fields. Other tools lack such support.
- (6) Legal Compliance: ARX and sdcMicro demonstrated higher compliance support than other tools. ARX provides formal anonymisation algorithms, quantitative risk assessment through three attacker models, attribute suppression for data minimisation, and detects major HIPAA identifiers, e.g. names, dates, phone, and email, on a best-effort basis. sdcMicro supports suppression and recoding methods for data minimisation and quasi-identifier protection with risk measurement capabilities including l-diversity and frequency-based risk calculations. However, neither tool confirmed support for purpose limitation, right to erasure verification, or deterministic encryption with key separation. Other tools lack comprehensive GDPR/HIPAA compliance features.
- (7) Interoperability: Arx, GreenMask and Neosync stood out for their API support, CI/CD pipeline integration, and environment-based configuration. As an R package, sdcMicro is scriptable and flexible but less accessible to users outside the R ecosystem. Amnesia and μ -ANT have limited extensibility due to tightly coupled GUIs or minimal interface options. ClustEm4Ano continues to be a research prototype and lacks extensibility documentation.
- (8) Format Compatibility: ARX, sdcMicro, and Amnesia support CSV and custom XML⁷ for metadata and hierarchies. GreenMask supports direct database integration with PostgreSQL⁸. Neosync connects to various SQL⁹ databases and APIs. However, none of the tools natively support healthcare-specific standards like HL7, FHIR, or SNOMED CT¹⁰, restricting direct applicability in clinical informatics without preprocessing.

⁷<https://www.w3.org/TR/xml>

⁸<https://www.postgresql.org>

⁹<https://www.w3schools.com/sql>

¹⁰https://www.bfarm.de/EN/Code-systems/Terminologies/SNOMED-CT/_node.html

- (9) **Data Utility:** ARX offers comprehensive visualisations and statistics. sdcMicro also calculates data utility scores using R-based statistical summaries but requires manual scripting, and complexity poses usability hurdles. SynDiffix emphasizes synthetic data utility, but lacks explicit metrics. Tools like Amnesia, GreenMask, and Neosync offer minimal support for utility assessment post-anonymisation, and ClustEm4Ano currently lacks any utility evaluation metrics.
- (10) **Visualisation:** ARX has interactive dashboards displaying privacy risks, equivalence classes, and attacker model results while sdcMicro has basic risk plots. Amnesia provides a minimal UI without risk visualisations. The recent tools like GreenMask, Neosync, and SynDiffix are largely headless or CLI-based, with no built-in dashboards. As for ClustEm4Ano, being purely academic, it lacks visual feedback.
- (11) **Attacker Simulation:** Only ARX offers explicit attacker model simulation and also visualises re-identification probabilities per attacker type. sdcMicro supports individual and global risk metrics but does not frame them within formal attacker models. SynDiffix addresses attacker resistance through differential privacy-like behaviour in query results. Tools, including Amnesia, Neosync, GreenMask, μ -ANT, and ClustEm4Ano, do not explicitly simulate or evaluate adversarial threats.
- (12) **Multilingual Support:** Amnesia and ARX offer internationalized UI, with ARX supporting multiple locales. Tools like GreenMask, Neosync, SynDiffix, and ClustEm4Ano currently do not offer multilingual options or region-specific customisation. This limits their applicability in deployments or healthcare systems that operate in non-English-speaking environments.

For research and data use, ARX and sdcMicro are best suited, given their support for formal models, risk assessment, and structured medical data. For development/testing environments, GreenMask and Neosync offer fast masking via DevOps integration. For

academic settings exploring categorical data anonymisation, ClustEm4Ano offers an experimental approach. For small-scale, GUI-driven anonymisation, Amnesia remains a lightweight option for even non-technical users. In some settings, hybrid pipelines may provide the best balance. For instance, hybrid pipelines, like GreenMask for operational masking combined with ARX for compliance checks, can offer a good balance.

4 Conclusion

As highlighted in previous studies [3], the trade-offs between utility, compliance, and usability showed that there one-size-fits-all tool does not exist. Some studies [22, 30] evaluated ARX, Amnesia, and sdcMicro, noting usability-compliance trade-offs and scalability limitations. Others [9] examined the anonymisation techniques for a set-valued data, which was a useful perspective for handling multi-value medical attributes. Earlier reviews [8, 31]) provided taxonomies of models and algorithms but lacked hands-on tool evaluations. Others [10] categorized tools descriptively without empirical testing or healthcare-specific scoring.

This paper offered a thorough empirical evaluation of open-source anonymisation tools for structured medical data where privacy risks are high and legal constraints are strict. We assessed several anonymisation tools using a unified framework. The results highlight a key trade-off; some tools like ARX and sdcMicro offer better privacy protections and regulation alignment, but are challenging to use, especially for non-technical users. Other tools like GreenMask and Neosync focus on developer usability and workflow integration, but often lack formal risk modeling or support for some anonymisation algorithms. This divergence reveals the need for use-case driven tool selection. Our results show that ARX and sdcMicro better suited for clinical research than other tools, while Neosync and GreenMask work better in development or internal testing pipelines. Our experiments show that many tools still lack support for healthcare ontologies, some medical formats, or legal guidelines.

This study makes the following contributions compared to similar previous studies:

- **Healthcare specific focus:** This paper offers a practical comparative evaluation of open-source anonymisation tools tailored to structured medical datasets, considering realistic regulations and clinical constraints.
- **Unified evaluation framework:** The scoring system combines ISO/IEC 25010 software quality standards with anonymisation criteria, enabling consistent benchmarking across diverse tools.
- **Inclusion of recent tools:** We also evaluate recent tools such as GreenMask, Neosync, SynDiffix, and ClustEm4Ano, which have not been evaluated yet.
- **Identification of gaps:** We identify the gaps in the current tools, e.g., some tools lack support for HL7/FHIR, have poor compatibility with clinical ontologies, and are missing attacker model simulations.
- **Practical deployment guidance:** By integrating usability, extensibility, and DevOps-readiness, this study offers deployment-focused insights relevant for both clinical research and development workflows.

Figure 1: Heatmap of the support level of each tested tool.

Table 2: Summary

Tool	Language	Anonymisation Algorithms	Main Features	Notable Limitations
ARX	Java	k-Anonymity, l-Diversity, t-Closeness, δ -Disclosure Privacy, β -Likeness, δ -Presence, k-map, Differential Privacy	GUI + CLI, attribute suppression, quantitative risk metrics (3 attacker models), HIPAA identifier detection, data utility analysis	Complicated, purpose limitation and right-to-erasure verification not supported
sdcMicro	R	k-Anonymity, l-Diversity, Statistical Disclosure Control (Suppression, Recoding, Micro-aggregation)	Risk estimation, frequency-based risk measures, data utility statistics, GUI available	No explicit attacker models
Amnesia	Java	k-Anonymity, km-Anonymity	Lightweight GUI, fast anonymisation via generalisation and suppression	No quantitative risk metrics; no HIPAA identifier support
Neosync	TypeScript	Synthetic Data + Deterministic Transformation	API-first design, CI/CD integration, database-native anonymisation	Many algorithms are missing; no risk simulation or compliance metrics
GreenMask	Go	Deterministic Pseudonymisation	PostgreSQL/Greenplum integration, DevOps-ready, in-database anonymisation	Many algorithms are missing; no risk assessment
SynDiffix	Python	Differential Privacy (Noise-based)	Synthetic data generation with statistical noise injection, query anonymisation	Limited formal anonymisation algorithm integration; usability features minimal
ClustEm4Ano	Python	Clustering-based Anonymisation	Medical data focus (diagnosis codes, clinical text), concept hierarchies	Experimental prototype; limited scalability; research-only
μ -ANT	Python	Ontology-based Generalisation	Conceptual generalisation for categorical data, semantic preservation	Limited scalability; research prototype; Many risk metrics are missing

Overall, this paper provides a structured, comparative guide to selecting anonymisation tools based on privacy strength, usability, domain applicability, and compliance readiness. As the multimedia and health data landscape expands, developing an improved anonymisation tool remains needed for safe, ethical, and legal data reuse.

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